

ENRICHING STUDENTS' ENGLISH LEXICON THROUGH AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN INNOVATIVE WAYS

Lutfullayeva Umida Ravshanbekovna

Head of the Department of "Pedagogy and Languages" at Tashkent University of Human
Sciences

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Abstract. *Authentic materials are widely used as an effective method in teaching English and play a major role in developing both students' linguistic and cultural competencies. This article discusses the enrichment of students' English lexicon through authentic materials by utilizing a wide range of innovative methods in order to facilitate learning process in English acquisition.*

Key words: *English, authentic materials, teaching methodology, linguistic skills, modern educational technologies, innovative methods, classroom environment, language competencies, utilization.*

In the context of modern globalization, improving the methodology of teaching new vocabulary of foreign languages is one of the urgent issues. In particular, the use of authentic materials in teaching English lexicon is of particular importance. Authentic materials are materials taken from real life, not specially adapted for language learners, and are found in newspapers and magazines, books, films, songs, Internet resources and other sources [1].

Several studies have been conducted by linguists and methodologists M.P. Breen, G.I. Voronina, E.V. Nosovich, R.P. Milrud, L. Van Lier, B. Tomalin, F. Mishan, Gebhard and others to clarify the concept of authentic materials in methodology and the problem of their utilization. There are several approaches to understanding what authentic materials are. In the process of dealing with this type of materials, we encounter the concept of “Authentic text”. W. Guariento and J. Morley noted about this concept that “Authentic text is a language produced in order to achieve some social goals in the society” [3]. Recent studies have shown that the use of authentic materials increases students’ motivation to learn a language, creates a real communication environment, and develops intercultural competence [2]. At the same time, special methodologies and approaches are necessary for the effective use of these materials. Because incorrectly selected or incorrectly presented authentic materials can have the opposite negative effect. Therefore, educators should be careful in choosing the appropriate authentic material for their students by paying attention to their age, ethnic background, religion and interests. Well-optimized authentic materials can lead both students and teacher to aim success in English language acquisition.

The relevance of this study is that today in Uzbekistan large-scale reforms are being carried out to improve the system of teaching foreign languages, to bring it into line with international standards. In this process, improving the methodology of using authentic materials is of great importance. The great thing about using authentic materials is that such sources are available everywhere. For example, authentic materials are not limited to articles in newspapers and magazines, but also songs, TV programs, films, radio, podcasts, menus, that is, anything written in English is considered authentic materials. This makes it easier for students to enrich their English vocabulary, and in addition, authentic materials provide students with the

opportunity to independently learn a foreign language. Innovative ways of teaching English language is necessary to be utilized by educators since doing so increases motivation of students in acquiring English language. Nowadays English teachers are eager to learn any innovative ways to teach their students effectively by creating them an appropriate atmosphere in the lesson and by inspiring them to learn English vocabulary without any difficulties which majority of L2 learners face during learning process.

There are several advantages in utilization of authentic materials in the teaching process. For example, when using such materials in the lesson, students encounter words, phrases, or grammatical devices that they have never encountered before. When listening to authentic materials, they learn to pronounce sounds and letters and concentrate effortlessly. Not only such materials are interesting for learners, but also teaching English language with the usage of them are demand of nowadays methodology since nowadays youth live in the technological era which means they are interested in new ways of learning languages.

The use of authentic materials or inauthentic materials in teaching English as a foreign language has been discussed by many linguists. One of them, Gilmore, has emphasized the difference between authentic materials and textbooks. According to Chavez and Monica, authentic materials are related to the motivation of students and this creates an opportunity to motivate them. They argue that authentic materials are more interesting, lively, and stimulating than inauthentic materials. These materials not only increase the interest of language learners in learning the language, but also teachers achieve better results by using them. Jacobson, a linguist and methodologist, also expressed his opinion about authentic materials. In his opinion, authentic materials are materials that are adapted to the context of language learners and are used in activities that are relevant to their lives [3]. Thus, Bieber emphasizes that authentic materials have the following characteristics:

- they are objective, unlike intuitive ones.
- when taken as a learning resource, authentic texts help develop communicative communication.
- authentic materials as learning materials bring different learning styles to the lesson process and, in addition, serve to increase student motivation.

Therefore, lectures or messages developed by writers or speakers in connection with everyday life are considered authentic materials. It is clear from this that authentic materials are not a part of invention or discovery, but a form of communication based on real life [2]

The use of authentic materials is important in the development of students' linguistic, cultural and communicative skills in the modern educational process. In the future, it is important to continue research on further integrating the use of authentic materials with modern educational technologies. This creates a great opportunity, in particular, to make English interactive and interesting. Utilization of authentic materials in innovative ways opens a wide door for both educators and learners in a long road called “English language acquisition”.

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